

Education and Society
(शिक्षण आणि समाज)

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Since 1977

The Quarterly dedicated to Education through Social Development and
Social Development through Education

July 2023

(Special Issue-1/ Volume-III)

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Theme of Human Relationship in Short Stories (Special Reference to Prem Chand, O'Henry and Anton Chekhov)

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Abstract:

For the Future Generation now it has become necessary to connect them with short stories. So that they will become closer to their traditions and values. They have to be good human being. The main aim of this study is to show the importance of short Stories in our life. With the help of short stories its very easy to express human emotions which motivates to improve the man personality. Through the present short stories of the paper their with the help of their characters different types of emotions are representing. These writers has given their readers wonderful selection of characters. Short Stories are just like an umbrella through which we learn more to creates a meaningful life. We wants our life to be successful. Stories are always full of experience which enrich our life

Keywords: Human, Relation, Contemporary, Ordinary, Requirement, Feelings, World Paper

Short Stories are shorter then novel and usually deals with only few characters. The short stories are always concerred with few episodes or scenes. Despite its limited scope it provide a complete its subject. Before 19th century short stories was not regarded as literary form. During 14th century the stories were present in Canterbury Tale by Chaucer. Story is a kind of prose fiction which can be read in one sitting. In this a complete picture of human life can be explored. In short its a bundle of all human emotions. Its a requirement of present world that once again we have to entre in the world of short stories. In the present stories the concept of human relationship has shown.

Munshi Prem Chand was the writer of Hindi and Urdu, in India. He born in Varanasi. His father was clerk in post office. His parents died so early. So he face immense poverty. He was an ordinary man but what makes him stand out are the numerous works which he wrote in his lifetime. He still read with great enthusiasm. As a story writer Prem chand had become a legend in own lifetime. The chief themes of his stories are rooted in the rural life with the cit social life appearing as a contrast to illustrate a complete picture of contemporary life.

Whenever we read his stories we can have the picture of Indian middle class society. Prem chand's stories are having different topics. In view of the variety of topics, he seems to have encompassed the entire sky of human world into his fold. Prem Chand's is showing us the condition of man in the society. He has written so many stories and novels which has a great impact in his reader's mind. Even today by their variegated layer

of thoughts and feelings. His humanism is not abstractly emotional but based on logical realism through which he reviled before his readers. His vivid evanescence of emotional idealism has given way to down-to-earth realism. His stories are just as the mirror of the society of India. He is always known as 'Katha-Samrat'. In short we can say that he has collected different topics from the society Jewel Box and pour the pearls of relationship into one necklace, so that we can easily see the Indian society its culture and human relationship. In Prem Chand's short stories we see the importance of human relationship.

Eid-Gaah -

The story is in typical Prem Chand's style, something which is a hallmark of his writing. This story is about one little boy Hamid, who lives with his grandmother AMINA. Hamid is going to fair on Eid with his friends and what happens there that will differentiate him from his friends. In this story we can see that such a small child Hamid who is near about four or five years, when his friends are busy and enjoying their sweets, toys etc. This boy is struggling with himself. We can see this mental condition with these lines-

'Mohsin asked Hamid to buy 'rewari'. How good they are, Hamid consider it just a joke. Mohsin offered it to him but immediately eat it himself. And then says-'O.K. this time I shall give you surely give by God. Come and take it Hamid answers, 'keep it. You think I have no money. Shammi,'Oh, you have only three paisa. What all will you buy from that'.

Mohmood, 'take, Gulabjamun from me. Hamid, Mohsin is naughty.

'Hamid, sweets are not that important. How many times it has written in book about bad are sweets?

Mohsin, But in heart, you must be waiting to have it why don't you buy on your own?"

Finally, he brings a pair of toys and gives it to his grandmother and says, 'Where was this chimta? I brought it. For how much? For three paisa. Reading this story gives a glimpse to an era gone by. It is tough to find people today across religious boundaries who would know about these details so closely. This story is full of love and positive human emotions.

Jurmana-

With respect to Prem Chand, Dalit writer and critics have generally looks favourably on his stories that depict Dalit characters are simple, moral, hard working, and compassionate. This is a story of a sweeper named Allaharakhi who was living a very miserable condition. Sometime she gets half salary due to Moht. Khairat Ali Khan, the safai daroga. He was well reputed as kind person, but Allaharakhi was the only one who rebuked by him. Though she was very laborious, even then she was fined. Whenever she tried to relax, daroga always appeared like a ghost. One's her child was with her, due to fever, the child hold her legs and pull her sari. Immediately she abused daroga and had not even finished her sentence, the daroga came. When she looked him, her heartbeats fastened. And daroga said-

'When you come to work why do you carry this nuisance along with you?

Why not leave her home?

Allaharakhi politely said,

She is not well sir, how could I leave her?

What happened to her? She is down with fever.

And you are so careless to throw her like this. She will die.'

Why don't you take leave?

I lose my pay, how will I carry on?

Allaharakhi was not satisfied. She had no peace of mind. She was wondering why daroga kept quiet being abused. Why did he not dismiss her there and then? When they reached the municipal office, they found already thousands of sweepers. A group of money lenders were also present to recover their dues. When her name called, she just walks slowly like a newlywed. The cashier paid her full salary -Rs.6/-.So she stood there expecting the cashier to ask her to return something. The cashier asked her, 'why don't you go? Then she said, 'but this is the full amount. The cashier looked at her surprisingly and said, 'What else do you want? Should you get less?

No fine?

No, no fine this time.'

So in this story again we can see the human relationship.

Poos Ki Raat-

Prem Chand brought realism to Hindi Literature. He successfully represent the feelings and mental states of farmers under charm of his psycho-analysis. Halku the hero of the story represents a typical Indian farmer, who born ,lives and dies in debt. Though he works very hard, even then he is unable to buy a woollen blanket. The story begins with the claim of debt by money- lender, Sohna. Halku was unable to pay the debt, so money-lender often abused him. This proves the ill treatment of upper class people for poor farmers.

'As there are only three rupees, 'said Halku's wife. We cannot return his money. We should buy a blanket instead. Since the harvest is not yet done we should wait.' It was a cold dark night; even stars seemed to shiver with cold. But Halku had no woollen clothes; he wrapped himself in an old cotton sheet. He lay on his cot in a corner of his field. His dog Jhabra lay under it. Neither Jhabra nor Halku could sleep. Halku smoked his clay pipe to keep away the cold. The cold went deep into his bones. Then he took Jhabra and made him sleep next to him. This kept both of them warm. Immediately Jhabra ran into the field from one corner to another. Some animals had entered in his field. Next morning when he walks up he saw his wife. She asked him to look at his fields where the crop had been eaten away by the cattle's this is the miserable condition of Indian farmers.

After reading these characters we can say that the rural Indian's and exploitation faced by a common man at the hands of priest, landlords, etc. His stories represents the ordinary Indian people as they are without any embellishment unlike many other contemporary writers. There is no hero in his stories. They described people as they are. His stories were so successful that's why so many films and T.V. serials are based on them

for example-Mazdoor 1934, Seva-Sadan 1933, Hera-Moti 1959, Nirmala-T.V. Serial.

Poos Ki Raat identifies layers of rural and urban society in their direct/indirect relation to the peasantry. The story unfolds along two levels of peasant and Zamidar tracing their respective lives with all their independent as well as intertwined problems. After reading all these stories it is quite clear that Prem Chand is at his best in his short stories weaving deeply personal narrative into a complex backdrop of social history and caste politics in conservative northern Indian. Even as he places the issues that fuelled social debates in the mouth of his characters. Prem Chand has always used his women characters as the lenses through which society is not simply seen. An examination of the way his fiction writings take in treatment of women would illustrate this ambivalence. Many of his stories bring out happiness that fills the lives of Indian women crushed in a society dominated by obsolete customs.

In his stories Prem Chand express the hollowness of middle class concern for honour when a respectable woman, caught in a mishap that may make people suspect her purity is rejected by her family forever. Many of his stories represent the problems created by dowry and the power of wealth. Prem Chand was a social reformer. He was the follower of Gandhi not Ambedker. So this is a significant matter for Dalit writers who feel that Dalit, Chatna was inspired slowly by Ambedker. We can see the picture of Indian poor people, specially Dalits. But if we really want to remove such types of problems so we have to work very hard. We must educate these people because if the person is educated so he is able to solve his problems. In short Gandhi and Ambedker work lot to remove these problems from the society.

The Last Leaf...

The Last Leaf has written by Sydney Porter famous by his pen name O'Henry. He was an American author. His stories are distinguished for their witty approaches, use of words, real characters. Those who have taken from the real world and with surprise theme. His tales also dramatised the common places and characters also. The Last Leaf has shown us the importance of nature in our life. O'Henry was himself was a lover of nature. Many of his stories published when he was in prison. In this story there are two main characters Sue and Johnsy as a good friends. When Johnsy fall seriously ill of Pneumonia. Sue tried her best to makes Johnsy to take interest in this world. But she failed finally she asked Mr. Behrman and discuss about the whole situation. She explained that Johnsy is counting the leaves of ivy outside the window. And she has discussed it with Sue that she will die when the last leaf will fall down. Finally on the rainy day this painter has painted the last leaf and in this way save her life but lost his own life. So again we noticed the human relationship in his story. The story has given us a message that hope give us strength to fight against our problems and get success also. Johnsy believes that she will died when the last leaf falls down. The doctor give pessimistic prognosis, she learned that the strength of a patient will to live greatly determines the effectiveness of the medical treatment. Behrman knew he could exploit her romantic attachment to last leaf by painting a fake version of the leaf with the help of imagery there

is a message behind the scene .The style of the writer is also very simple so that everyone can understand . Stories always give message to all the readers and common man too .We all are leaving now in the technological world where man has become a machine. Stories pour human values in our self so now it has become a necessity to rethink about the importance of stories in our life

The Lament...

Anton Chekhov is a Russian writer. As story is the best source to convey the message very easily. Man as a human being always wants to share his problems with others but in this materialistic world no one has time. In the present story the writer has wonderfully expressed the character of Lona . The story starts with this line.. 'To whom shall I tell my grief ' .

The story tells about a father and his great despair for his dead son, Lona the father is a Russian sleigh driver who wants to share his grief with others but no one has time to listen him .This story has shown the harshness of human nature .It shows the lack of human involvement and compassion towards one man's grief .Lona tries three times to share his pain with others unsuccessfully failed .In the last finally he turned back towards his horse to the stable . Lona wants that someone listen the details of his son's death yet no one has showed any interest. This incident drove him into deeper grief .In the end he poured his heard out to his horse and she listened. With the help of this story this is clear to us that we all need to have human relationship not only with man but to whom those who have heart. This is the quality of a story that it always connects with their readers . Now- a- Days everybody has no time , they just think about them self and busy with technology .So stories are the best source to pour values in new generation and build a strong future .The young generation has to know their tradition and values of their life . With the help of all these stories it is clear to all that stories pass the message to the readers very easily in a simple way. In a short canvas all human emotions can be seen with the help of different character

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